

ISic1519

I.Sicily inscription 1519

Language

Ancient Greek

Type

funerary

Material

slate

Object**Editor**

Jonathan Prag

Principal Contributor

Jonathan Prag

Contributors

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Autopsy

No Autopsy

Last Change

2020-11-26 - Simona Stoyanova restructured bibliography

Place of origin (ancient)

Syracusae

Place of origin (modern)

Siracusa

Provenance

Catacomb of S.Giovanni

Coordinates**Current Location**

Italy, Sicily, Siracusa, Museo Archeologico
Regionale Paolo Orsi, inventory 14610

Physical Description

Dimensions

Height cm

Width cm

Depth cm

Layout

Execution

Engraved

Letter Forms

Letter heights:

Line 1: mm

Interlineation

Interlineation line 1 to 2: mm

Text

1. [Ἐνθάδε] κῆτε Γα
2. [λήνη] τελευτᾷ μη
3. [νῆς]επτε[μ]βρίω τῆς
4. δεκάτες πρὸ ἰσ(ταμένου) □
5. τελευτᾷ ἐτῶν τρι[ά] κοντα

Apparatus

Text after Orsi 1895

Translation

Commentary

Digital identifiers:

TM 645019

Bibliography

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Orsi, P. 1895. Insigne epigrafe del cimitero di S. Giovanni in Siracusa. *Römische
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